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Experience from practice

Iskustvo iz prakse

THE USE OF THE DESIGN THINKING METHOD IN TEACHING SERBIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN HIGH SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to present the use of the Design Thinking teaching method in Serbian language and literature classes within a vocational high school, specifically across two third-grade classes and its contribution to enhancing the quality of the instructional process. The paper presents the phases of the Design Thinking method through a concrete example implemented over a course of six periods per class. The topic covered belongs to the field of lexicology: Idioms in the Serbian Language. By progressing through all stages of the Design Thinking method implementation, students developed creative and critical thinking, team spirit, collaboration, and communication; they also advanced their cross-curricular competences and digital skills, becoming co-creators of their own learning alongside the teacher. The overall quality of the classes was improved, and the students became motivated, active participants in their Serbian language lessons. It can be concluded that integrating modern methods, in this case Design Thinking, into teaching practice significantly raises the quality of classes, leading to higher student satisfaction and success.

Keywords: Design Thinking method, active learning, creative and critical thinking, high school, Serbian language and literature

Introduction

This paper provides an analysis of the use of the Design Thinking method (DTM) in teaching Serbian language and literature in a vocational high school. The aim was to examine the extent to which this method influences the increase of student activity during class, boosts motivation, concentration, and attention, and develops critical and creative thinking, meaning, the goal is to place the student in an active role both in creating the curriculum and in the actual execution of the lesson.

Design Thinking is a contemporary teaching method that originated in industry and refers to design thinking. Dorst (2011, p. 525) states that the core challenge of design reasoning is “performing the complex creative feat of the parallel creation of a thing (object, service, system) and its way of working”. It emerged when David Kelley, who in 1977 studied at Stanford University in a program that combined engineering and art, introduced Design Thinking principles in his

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company IDEO (2012, 2019). In 2004, he founded the Hasso Plattner Institute of Design at Stanford, better known as the d.school. This is the first official institution dedicated to Design Thinking, whose main goal is the development, teaching, and implementation of Design Thinking, and which continues to significantly influence professionals around the world working with Design Thinking (Baričević, 2022, p. 15).

Prestigious universities, business schools, and highly successful companies have adopted the Design Thinking method and use it for innovation in their respective fields. Design Thinking is still evolving; it is being applied in an increasing number of areas and is continuously being researched and improved (Baričević, 2022, p. 6). It can be said that it is highly significant for problem-solving and innovation development, as it combines creative and analytical thinking. In the implementation of DTM, the core principle is to place the student at the center, to understand the problem, and then to collaboratively arrive at a solution (or multiple solutions) through the process, while also showing students that mistakes are an integral part of the path toward finding solutions.

Methods

DTM was implemented in two third-grade classes of four-year vocational study programs, with a weekly workload of three lessons, during the period March - April 2026, at the Secondary School of Electrical Engineering and Civil Engineering "Nikola Tesla" (classes were selected in which reduced student motivation for classroom work was observed, as well as noticeable difficulties in maintaining concentration and a very limited active and passive vocabulary). The following phases of DTM were implemented (empathy, define, ideation, prototype, and testing) over the course of six teaching lessons.

Empathy is the first and a key phase in the DTM, as it involves getting to know and understanding students, that is, "it is necessary to understand why users do something in a certain way, their physical and emotional needs, how they think about the world, and what is meaningful to them" (Baričević, 2022, p. 20). In the empathy phase, the following methods of investigating students' needs were used: conversations with students during classes, in which they expressed their opinions, attitudes, and suggestions related to the subject matter (how interesting it is to them), teaching methods, as well as reasons for their lack of motivation (the most common answers were that they do not like reading, that grammar is not useful to them, etc.); observation was also used, as well as note-taking as an important method. The teacher observed students' behavior during class, how much they followed the lesson, in which situations they were most involved, how many of them read the assigned material for class, and how well they applied orthography in emails, on the board, in school assignments, etc. Finally, a questionnaire was conducted with all students from both classes, consisting of four questions. Students evaluated their answers on a scale from 1 to 5 (1 being the lowest score, 5 the highest), and the last question was open-ended. The questionnaire included the following questions: assess your participation in class (work, activity, participation in discussion, analysis, etc.); evaluate the teacher's work (presentation style, lesson organization, assessment methods, classroom atmosphere); I believe that digital tools should be used more in class; suggestions for improving classes (how to make lessons more engaging and how I can be an active participant). The results of the questionnaire showed that students realistically assessed their participation in class (very low scores), as well as the teacher's work, but most importantly, they showed initiative in the form of suggestions for improving lessons in which they would be active participants (project-based teaching, use of digital tools, group work). It was recognized that students want to be involved in the creation of the teaching process and that they want change.

This was followed by problem definition, for which the “Problem Tree” technique was used, i.e., “problem tree analysis (PTA) - also known as root cause analysis - is an approach to project planning popular among development agencies. In PTA, individuals work together to break down a specific issue into its causes and effects” (Catavello, 2023).

The technique was implemented in both third-grade classes in March 2026 during Serbian language and literature lessons, with students divided into six groups of five students each. Each group was given instructions on how to complete the “Problem Tree.”

Results

The instructions provided guidelines for work: roots - to list the causes of low motivation for participation in class activities; trunk - to identify the main problem in class; branches and leaves - to list the consequences of inactivity and lack of motivation in Serbian language and literature classes.

Afterwards, a “Problem Tree” was drawn on the board, each group presented its examples for the trunk, roots, branches, and leaves, and the teacher recorded the answers on the board. The following answers were obtained:

Trunk: the central problem being addressed (“Students are not active in class: they do not listen, they mechanically write down notes, they have no ideas, and the answers they give are of very low quality”). Roots: all previous causes that create the problem (texts seem boring, grammar is difficult, they do not see the purpose of learning, digital habits, lack of motivation for any work). Branches and leaves: consequences resulting from the main problem (decreased interest in the subject, inactivity in class, inability to express themselves properly, poor literacy, underdeveloped critical thinking). At the center of this technique was a very active discussion, from which the problem was defined. The goal of implementing the “Problem Tree” technique was for students and the teacher together to define the problem that would be addressed in the following period.

On the basis of the second phase, the problem definition phase, and with the help of the “Problem Tree” technique, a shared problem was defined: *“How might we ensure that everyone is active in Serbian language and literature classes?”*

During the third phase, the ideation phase, creative thinking, teamwork, and the willingness to accept the ideas of other participants are emphasized. For this phase, the brainstorming technique was used, which was implemented in two third-grade classes in March 2026 during Serbian language lessons. Brainstorming is a problem-solving technique in which individuals or groups spontaneously generate ideas in order to find possible solutions (Merriam -Webster, n.d.). Using the brainstorming technique, all students in both classes listed a large number of ideas for the next phase. Each student wrote down their ideas on paper, which were then written on the board, including those that were repeated several times. Brainstorming technique was chosen because it enables the spontaneous listing of a large number of ideas, making it easier to select high-quality ones from a large quantity. Students were also instructed that criticism of any suggestion or idea was not allowed. Afterwards, the ideas were selected using the dot voting technique. Dot voting technique enables the participation of all students by having each student select three ideas from the board (or projector). It quickly allows the identification and selection of the most interesting ideas (in the case of the two third-grade classes: quizzes, projects, creative writing, and the use of ICT tools) for the next phase, prototyping.

Phase 4, the prototyping phase, began with a reminder of the problem being addressed in order to keep students focused. The chosen topic/field was lexicology, specifically the lesson unit:

Phraseology and Idioms in the Serbian Language (in accordance with the teaching and learning plan).

Based on the collectively generated ideas and the students' personal interests, tasks for the execution of the lesson were distributed as follows:

- Design a quiz using the Kahoot tool to test knowledge of idioms in the Serbian language, conducted as pair work (students receive precise instructions for the task).
- Create a test using the Testmoz tool to test knowledge of idioms in the Serbian language, conducted as pair work (students receive precise instructions for the task).
- Make an interactive poster-infographic in Canva on the topic of "Idioms in the Serbian Language", conducted as pair work (students receive precise instructions for the task).
- Using SWAY, integrate these tasks along with a prepared survey for other students, who will evaluate the participation and activities after the prototyping phase.
- Using AI, write an essay on the topic "A Day at School / At Home," utilizing as diverse a range of idioms as possible.

In Phase 5, the testing phase, testing and improvement were conducted in a real classroom environment, during the lesson. Following this, a survey was conducted (Mentimeter), accompanied by a discussion with the students (as students answered each question in the survey, an analysis would immediately follow). This phase is crucial because it serves as a roadmap for future improvement. The key element of testing is uncovering what did not work best, in order to see how useful the designed activities actually are for the students. Throughout the testing process itself, trust is built not only between the students and the teacher, but also among the students themselves.

The results following the analysis of the implementation of the Design Thinking teaching method in Serbian language and literature classes in two third-grade vocational school classes, conducted in April 2026, show a very high level of student satisfaction in class (95%), followed by student engagement levels also exceeding 90%. Lessons were rated as interesting by 98% of students, 96% confirmed that they freely expressed their ideas, and 97% reported an increased level of cooperation and communication among students in the classroom, while 100% of students expressed a desire for the continued application of the DTM in teaching. The lessons were of higher quality, the atmosphere was more pleasant, and ICT tools were used, which is further supported by the full achievement of the set learning outcomes (assessment was conducted through student-created and student-completed tests, discussions, and presentations of student work). It can be concluded that the implementation of this method in the teaching process develops skills necessary for the 21st century: critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, and digital competences.

Conclusion

The use of the DTM primarily has a positive impact on student motivation, making the class active and raising the overall quality of instruction. By integrating student ideas into the lesson, students become co-creators of the educational process alongside the teacher. Through the realization of such activities, cross-curricular correlation occurs spontaneously, and cross-curricular competences are significantly developed, thereby contributing to raising the quality of the lifelong learning process. It can be concluded that by using the DTM, students become creators of their own learning; they "learn how to learn" and foster an atmosphere that promotes creative learning, critical reflection, empathy, and respect for the ideas of others, while nurturing and developing team spirit. Above all, throughout the learning process, they experience satisfaction and the freedom to express

their ideas, without fearing mistakes, understanding instead that errors are simply a stepping stone to a new solution.

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PRIMENA DESIGN THINKING METODE U NASTAVI SRPSKOG JEZIKA I KNJIŽEVNOSTI U SREDNJOJ ŠKOLI

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Apstrakt

Cilj rada je da prikaže primenu Design Thinking nastavne metode na časovima srpskog jezika i književnosti u srednjoj stručnoj školi, u dva odeljenja trećeg razreda i njen doprinos podizanju kvaliteta nastavnog procesa. U radu su prikazane faze Design Thinking metode na konkretnom primeru koji je realizovan u dva odeljenja po šest časova. Obrađena je tema iz oblasti leksikologije, frazeologizmi u srpskom jeziku. Polazeći kroz sve faze Design Thinking metode učenici su razvijali kreativno i kritičko mišljenje, timski duh, saradnju, komunikaciju, unapredili su svoje međupredmetne kompetencije, digitalne veštine i postali kreatori sopstvenog učenja zajedno sa nastavnikom. Kvalitet časova je poboljšán, a učenici su postali motivisani i aktivni učesnici časova srpskog jezika. Može se zaključiti da je upotrebom savremenih metoda, u ovom slučaju Design Thinking metode, u nastavnoj praksi značajno podignut kvalitet časova, a učenici su zadovoljniji i uspešniji.

Ključne reči: Design Thinking metoda, aktivno učenje, kreativno i kritičko mišljenje, srednja škola, srpski jezik i književnost

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